

Parental Incarceration and Children's School Drop-out*

A Limited Study for West Bengal

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Abstract

Dropout from school poses the greatest challenge towards achieving the desired educational policy of government despite codified legislations and state-sponsored projects that aim to bring the students within the arena of school set-up. Various researchers have addressed this issue from various perspectives corroborating their viewpoint by various governmental and independent organizational reports. All these clearly show the vastness and complexity of school dropout resulting from varied socio-economic factors as well as lacunae of policy and infrastructure. In addition to the determinants of school dropouts in India which can be found in the 75th round of NSS data, whereby it is found that 74% of student population aged 18 years and above drop out from school before reaching the 12th standard inclusive of various religious, economic and caste-based groups, the students with incarcerated parents form another determinant of school dropouts. The present study will try to build a bridge between the indicator termed as "Incarcerated Parents" and its effect on school dropout, and find possible ways to speed up justice delivery for parents and children. This is a limited study as it is solely based on secondary data which is scarce for the chosen state. Whether incarcerated parents form the population of convicted or under-trial or detenue within prisons is inconsequential for this study, as in all the cases the school-going children of incarcerated people face enormous lack of social and emotional stability, parental care and quality peer-company, and are altogether deprived of their human rights.

[**KEYWORDS:** *Incarcerated Parent, Child, School, Dropout, Education, Prison*]

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1 Introduction

Children’s educational right in a country so vast, complex and home to so much multifarious cultures and customs like India is not something that is monolithic and homogeneous. Hence, to impose and implement such right as legal as well as *Fundamental*¹ is very difficult to achieve, be it by the *state* and/ or any other agency. And if the question arises of the children of those parent either or both of whom are being incarcerated in prison, the status of such parent’s children are worse and hard to even imagine in a societal structure like us. Our Apex Court has time and again enumerated that a prisoner is a person who is inherently entitled to all the basic human rights, human dignity and sympathy.² From a plethora of cases, newspaper reports and other articles, we can see that majority of the prisoners housed in several jails and prisons in India are from marginalised section of the society. These marginalised sections are socially stigmatised and are essentially stigmatised as deemed criminal (Dixit, 2023)³. Given the extremely slow speed of our criminal justice system to declare a prisoner as convicted or acquitted, the under-trial prisoners face immense incarceration inside the prison or jail. In a report accessed on 26.01.2025, we can see an estimate of prison population in India ranged over twenty years, as enumerated in the following table⁴:

Year	Number in pre-trial/ remand imprisonment	Percentage of total prison population	Pre-trial/ remand population rate (per 100,000 of national population)
2000	193,627	71.2%	18
2005	237,076	66.2%	21
2010	240,098	65.1%	20
2015	282,076	67.2%	22
2020	371,848	76.1%	27
2022	434,302	75.8%	31

Table 1: Indian Prison Population List

Hence, it can be seen that with increasing years from 2000 to 2022, the rate of incarceration

¹INDIA CONST. art. 19

²T K Gopal v. State of Karnataka, (2000) 6 S.C.C. 168 (India).

³Himanshu Dixit, *Child of Incarcerated Parents: A Deemed Criminal*, ILI LAW REVIEW-2023 (Summer, e-ISSN-0976-1489) (2018), https://ili.ac.in/pdf/14._Himanshu_Dixit_F

⁴WORLD PRISON BRIEF, <https://www.prisonstudies.org/country/india>

ation in Indian prisons has increased from 18 to 31. This incarcerated people represent those who were yet to receive sentence, or are under-trial prisoners, and their percent share among the whole of prison population is shocking. The outcome of this is that those incarcerated in prison, become deemed criminals in outside world and society does accept them but with a stigma. These people do have fundamental rights as other members of the society, but simply due to the reason of their being incarcerated in prison, this fundamental right might get shrieked⁵.

The problem arising from this is what this paper is aimed at. The children of those incarcerated in prison, be they one parent or both, be they already convicts, or under-trials, face a harsh reality when they encounter the society on their own and subsequently labelled as the 'children of criminals'. These children are formally divided into two categories⁶ - one that live with their mother inside prison bars, and are under 6 years of age, and the second category are those who live outside the prison. Both are labelled as the children of prisoners. Children, who are in the formative years of their psycho-social development, become helpless and prone to societal evils. For those who live inside the prison with their mother are born inside the prison. India is a country which does not recognize father as the primary caregiver for a baby child, and hence children born inside the prison live with their mother, even if the father of the child is outside the prison. this poses a serious threat to the children of the prisoners as the number of female prisoners for India is seen to be increasing as per the following study⁷:

Year	Number of female prisoners	Percentage of total prison population	Female prison population rate (per 100,000 of national population)
2000	9,089	3.3%	0.9
2005	13,986	3.9%	1.2
2010	15,037	4.1%	1.2
2015	17,834	4.3%	1.4
2020	20,046	4.1%	1.4
2022	23,772	4.1%	1.7

Table 2: Indian Prisons Female Population List

⁵Sunil Batra (II) v. Delhi Administration, (1980) 3 S.C.C. 488 (India)

⁶JOAN PETERSILIA, FROM CELL TO SOCIETY: WHO IS RETURNING HOME? (New York, Cambridge University Press, 1st ed., 2005).

⁷WORLD PRISON BRIEF, <https://www.prisonstudies.org/country/india>

Both the Judiciary and Legislature have come time again for the well-being and rescue of the children who are circumstantially imprisoned with their parents. For this extensive data collection, survey regarding the physical and psychological status of the children in prison have been carried out. After the celebrated Upadhyay⁸ case, the Apex court has settled the position on this matter. It has stated in its landmark judgement after careful consideration of the plight of children in prison that these are to be considered as a distinct group by the government and take actions to mitigate their suffering such as neglect of health and hygiene, insubstantial food and inadequate clothing, prison vices etc. It has reiterated this issue in another case and pointed that jail visits be streamlined and deficiency in communication be looked upon.⁹

Our focus in this paper is limited to the study of those children who are not living inside jails with their parent(s), but are in outside world and face multitudes of hardships in their daily life. Among those problems, majority of which are beyond tabular representation, we have chosen only one parameter and that also for one single state. We are chiefly concerned here with the factor of school drop-out of those children in West Bengal whose parents, either one or both, are incarcerated in prison. This is a limited study due to the poor availability of data regarding this correlation. Only the state of West Bengal has been chosen as reference state for this correlative study of school drop-out and incarceration of parents.

2 Children - where do they fit within our justice system?

Children are the most vulnerable section of our society. In a socio-economic set up of a country like India, where the GDP shows depressing downwards trends, and after the COVID-19 breakout, the economy of our country further worsened.¹⁰ Those who are migrant workers, be it seasonal or not, had huge impact on their livelihood after prolonged nation-wide lock-down imposed by the Central Government as well as the various state governments time to time. As the prison population of India comprises chiefly of people from lower strata of society, there happens to be a connection between crime and underdeveloped socio-economic condition. Given that, we are connected here only with the children

⁸R.D Upadhyay v. State of Uttar Pradesh, (1996) 3 S.C.C. 422 (India)

⁹Rama Murthy v. State of Karnataka, (1997) 2 S.C.C. 642 (India)

¹⁰Sahoo, P., & Ashwani, *COVID-19 and Indian economy: Impact on growth, manufacturing, trade and MSME sector*, 21(5), GLOBAL BUSINESS REVIEW, 1159-1183 (2020)

of the incarcerated parents, and that also of those parents whose children are not living with them inside the prison. For this, first let us briefly discuss about various legal provisions regarding children of our country.

2.1 Brief analysis of existing Laws

2.1.1 Regarding well-being of children

Convention on the Rights of the Child¹¹: India being a participating state-party to the UNCRC¹² and acceded to it on 11th December, 1992 the resolutions are enforceable and legally binding upon India. It establishes a comprehensive framework to safeguard children's rights globally. Its central mandate is to protect children, ensuring that they are shielded from harm, abuse, neglect and exploitation.

The Juvenile Justice Act¹³: This Act has been the mother Act that relates juveniles who are in conflict of law and those who are in need of care and protection. The Act defines juveniles as a person who has not attained the age of 18 years. It enumerates and defines *child in need of care and protection*¹⁴, whereby it specifies the conditions whereupon a child can be protected under this Act. This Act proposes the establishment of various institutions, such as shelter homes¹⁵ and special homes¹⁶ for the purpose of rehabilitation of children and adjudication of the matters relating to them. Most importantly, this Act proposes to establish a Child Welfare Committee¹⁷ in each states of the country, which will enquire into the cases of those children who are need of care and protection and accordingly take steps to rehabilitate them. This rehabilitation is inclusive of sending the children to homes and/or making arrangements for their social rehabilitation through adoption¹⁸.

After the enactment of the Principal Act, a number of Rules have been made and amended time to time so as to cater to the children's interest with changing socio-cultural

¹¹Convention on the Rights of the Child; Adopted and opened for signature, ratification and accession by General Assembly Resolution 44/25 of 20 November 1989; entry into force 2 September 1990, in accordance with article 49 [hereinafter UNCRC]

¹²*supra* note 11

¹³The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2000, No. 56, Acts of Parliament, 2000 (India)

¹⁴§ 2(d), clauses i-ix; *supra* note 13

¹⁵§ 2(u) of the Act, *supra* note 13

¹⁶§ 2(v) of the Act, *supra* note 13

¹⁷§ 29 of the Act; *supra* note 13

¹⁸CHAPTER IV of the Act.; *supra* note 13

scenario. The latest being the Model Amendment Rules, 2022¹⁹, where there have been made detailed provisions for the registration of Child Care Institutions²⁰ and Group Foster Care²¹ thus streamlining the management of the care and protection set up for the children. The amended Rules have, in letters and spirit, upheld the children as distinct persons of this society, and have given importance to their suggestions on matters related to their care and protection.

Protection of Child Rights Act²²: India is a signatory to the UN General Assembly Summit in 1990 which adopted a Declaration named UNCRC. As India acceded to that treaty, in order to protect the interest of the children, this legislation was enacted. This was to give effect to the policies adopted by our Government in this regard, and standards prescribed in the UNCRC. This Act prescribes for the formation of a Commission with duties to protect the interest of children and also to enquire any violation of the rights of a child. The functions and powers of the Commission are enumerated in the Act²³.

POCSO Act²⁴: POCSO is a gender-neutral legislation. In this Act, a *child* is defined as a person who is below the age of 18 years and is either a male or female. The offender may as well be a male or female. This Act was passed to comprehensively deal with the issue of offences committed against children, the punishments and creating a support system for the victims. It categorizes three acts of offence that are punishable under this Act, namely, sexual assault²⁵, aggravated sexual assault²⁶ sexual harassment²⁷ and using a child for pornography²⁸. This Act also provides for the establishment of Special Courts²⁹ for the purpose of providing a speedy trial in cases of commission of offences against a child. Hence, it is a comprehensive and almost exhaustive legislation for the protection and care of children, and it incorporates within its ambit those who are living in judicial custody with their incarcerated parents. Subsequent Rules have been made under this Act, and amended

¹⁹Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Model Amendment Rules, 2022; G.S.R. 678(E), 1st September, 2022

²⁰§ 16 of the Rules, *supra* note 19

²¹§ 17 of the Rules, *supra* note 19

²²Commissions for Protection of Child Rights Act, 2005, No. 4, Acts of Parliament, 2006 (India)

²³§ 13 of the Act, *supra* note 22

²⁴Protection of Children From Sexual Offences Act, 2012, No. 12, Acts of Parliament, 2012 (India)

²⁵§ 3 of the Act, *supra* note 24

²⁶§ 9 of the Act, *supra* note 24

²⁷§ 11 of the Act, *supra* note 24

²⁸§ 13 of the Act, *supra* note 24

²⁹§ 28 of the Act, *supra* note 24

time to time, the latest being the Rules³⁰ of 2020, made under the Principal Act³¹ of 2012, where the process of care and protection of children in need have been delineated more extensively.

2.1.2 Regarding educational rights of children

National Policy of Education, 1986³²: Although not much is to said here about NPE-1986, let us quote from its Introductory, which says in a point³³ that:

“In the Indian way of thinking, a human being is a positive asset and a precious national resource which needs to be cherished, nurtured and developed with tenderness and care, coupled with dynamism. Each individual’s growth presents a different range of problems and requirement, at every stage - from the womb to the tomb. The catalytic action of education in this complex and dynamic growth process needs to be planned meticulously and executed with great sensitivity.”

Hence, the idea was clear - to achieve a holistic development of each individual from the very beginning. Let us not delve within this discussion as the time has changed a lot with a vast change in educational goals and morality in the twenty-first century. Just to add one point that the NPE-1986 had provided for the establishment of Day Care Centres³⁴ for those children of ages 0-6 years as a support service for working women belonging to the poorer section of the society. But this Policy did not specifically provided for those children whose parents are being incarcerated in prisons and jails.

Right to Education Act³⁵: This is the most comprehensive legislation regarding education of children in India to date. For enacting this legislation, a Constitutional Amendment³⁶ was done, and a new Article³⁷ was inserted. By doing this Constitutional Amendment, India became one of those 135 countries of the world to make the right to education as a *Fundamental Right*. From this we can understand the legislative intent of the parliament and

³⁰Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Rules, 2020; G.S.R. 165(E), 9th March, 2020

³¹§ 45 of the Act, *supra* note 24

³²Published by the MINISTRY OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT, GOVERNMENT OF INDIA

³³PART I, § 1.10 *supra* note 32

³⁴PART V, § 5.1; *supra* note 32

³⁵The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009, No. 35, Acts of Parliament, 2009 (India)

³⁶The Constitution (Eighty Sixth Amendment) Act, 2002

³⁷INDIA CONST. art. 21A *amended* by The Constitution (Eighty Sixth Amendment) Act, 2002

its importance.

RTE Act, along with Article 21A came into effect on 1st April, 2010. This Act provides for the free and compulsory elementary education³⁸ of the children from ages 6-14 years³⁹. Thus, 'compulsory education' casts an obligation on the appropriate Government and local authorities to provide and ensure admission, attendance and completion of elementary education by all children in the 6-14 age group. And this also in a neighbourhood school. The horizon of this enabling legislation extends to the fact that those children who are non-admitted⁴⁰, shall have to be admitted to a class of his/ her appropriate age. This Act also specifically bans i) mental harassment and physical punishment⁴¹, ii) screening of children for admission⁴², iii) capitation fees⁴³.

Thus, RTE Act provides an all-inclusive educational legislation where the appropriate Government, whether Central, State or Local Body are mandated to provide free and compulsory education for the children of 6-14 years, and also create framework and infrastructure for this purpose, including teachers' qualification. The kernel of this Act is that no children of the target age group will be left out of school, hence removing it from the *Directive Principles of State Policy*, and making it a *Fundamental Right*.

The RTE Act defines a *child belonging to disadvantaged group*⁴⁴ as one who has any kind of disability, or a child belonging to SC, ST or any other socially and educationally backward class or such other group having disadvantage owing to social, cultural, economical, geographical, linguistic, gender or such other factor. This provision has an inclusive connotative sense, as it can incorporate within its ambit any child who, by its circumstances and/ or any other contingent conditions, has been placed within the brackets of disadvantaged group. Hence, this bracket can easily accommodate those children belonging to the target age-group whose parents are being incarcerated in prisons and jails. Even if this broader legislative intent, there has been lacunae in engaging these children within the school curriculum.

³⁸RTE 2009, § 8, *supra* note 35

³⁹RTE 2009, § 3, *supra* note 35

⁴⁰RTE 2009, § 4, *supra* note 35

⁴¹RTE 2009, § 17, *supra* note 35

⁴²RTE 2009, § 13, *supra* note 35

⁴³RTE 2009, § 13, *supra* note 35

⁴⁴RTE 2009, § 2, cl. d., *supra* note 35

2.2 Brief analysis of various provisions of *our* Constitution

There was a major amendment to the Constitution in 2002⁴⁵, whereby the following Articles were introduced which directly provide for the educational rights of children. In its Statement of Objects and Reasons, it was stated that⁴⁶:

”The Constitution of India in a Directive Principle contained in article 45, has made a provision for free and compulsory education for all children up to the age of fourteen years within ten years of promulgation of the Constitution. We could not achieve this goal even after 50 years of adoption of this provision. The task of providing education to all children in this age group gained momentum after the National Policy of Education (NPE) was announced in 1986. The Government of India, in partnership with the State Governments, has made strenuous efforts to fulfil this mandate and, though significant improvements were seen in various educational indicators, the ultimate goal of providing universal and quality education still remains unfulfilled. In order to fulfil this goal, it is felt that an explicit provision should be made in the Part relating to Fundamental Rights of the Constitution.”

Following are the three Articles which are inserted by the Constitution (Eighty-sixth Amendment) Act, 2002, among which the first is a *Fundamental Right*, the second one is a *Directive Principle of State Policy*, and the last one is a *Fundamental Duty*.

Article 21A: This Article was added to the Constitution of India by the Constitution (Eighty-sixth Amendment) Act, 2002 after Article 21, which is originally enshrined for *Fundamental Rights*. Thus, Right to Education is basically a fundamental right approved by our constitution. Let us be reminded that the right to education is not a fundamental right as it is placed in the relevant Part of the Constitution, but, as it is a fundamental human right to be enjoyed by all, it is placed in the Constitution in Part III. The Article states that: *The State shall provide free and compulsory education to all children of the age of six to fourteen years in such manner as the State may, by law, determine.*

Article 45: This Article was substituted in place of the old one, and it says that: ”The State shall endeavour to provide early childhood care and education for all children until they complete the age of six years”. This comes under Directive Principles of State Policy

⁴⁵The Constitution (Eighty Sixth Amendment) Act, 2002

⁴⁶https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/upload_document/amend86.pdf, accessed on 4th February, 2025

and is non-justiciable. This casts an obligation upon the State to take over the particular responsibility.

Article 51A(K): The eighty-sixth constitution amendment act of 2002 inserted another *Fundamental Duty* of the parent as a clause after J, which read as: *Who is a parent or guardian to provide opportunities for education to his child or, as the case may be, ward between the age of six and fourteen years.* Thus this clause provides that the parents, in exercise of their Fundamental Duty, must ensure so that their ward between the age of six and fourteen years, get opportunity for education. But this duty cannot be performed by a parent in an incarcerated situation, while they are inside prison or jail. Thus, be it the appropriate Government or the parents, the children altogether have an inalienable right to education and that right can not be taken away by any legislation and/ or by any figment of administrative understanding.

2.3 Brief analysis of various Supreme Court Cases

There are numerous cases and rulings by our Apex Court regarding the educational rights of children, but let us limit ourselves to only two landmark judgements which mark the welfare nature of the Indian State.

Mohini Jain case:⁴⁷ The *ratio* of Mohini Jain case is that the right to education is a *fundamental right* under **Article 21** of the Indian Constitution, which guarantees the right to life and liberty. The court also ruled that the collection of capitation fees is a violation of the fundamental right, as it restricts their access to education. Moreover, it emphasized that the state has a constitutional obligation to provide education to its citizens.

Unni Krishnan case:⁴⁸ The *ratio* of the Unni Krishnan case is that the *right to education* is a *fundamental right* under **Article 21** (Right to Life) of the Indian Constitution, but limited to children until the age of 14. The Supreme Court held that the state is constitutionally obligated to provide free and compulsory elementary education to all children within this age group. Beyond 14 years, the state's responsibility to provide education is subject

⁴⁷Miss Mohini Jain vs. State of Karnataka and Ors., 1992, AIR 1858, 1992 SCR (3) 658

⁴⁸Unni Krishnan, J.P. and Ors. vs. State of Andhra Pradesh and Ors., AIR 2178, 1993 SCR (1) 594, 1993 (1) SCR 594, (1993) 1 JT 474 (SC).

to its economic capacity and developmental priorities. This ruling partially overruled the broader interpretation in the Mohini Jain case and laid the groundwork for the 86th Constitutional Amendment (2002), which introduced Article 21A enshrining *free and compulsory education* for children aged 6–14 as a fundamental right.

3 Status of Children’s School Drop-out in West Bengal

3.1 Introduction

The problem of dropout of children from school in any level for the state of West Bengal has been studied, analysed and documented by a large number institutions, educationalists and scholars, both in academic and non-academic spheres. Notable among them are by Levy⁴⁹ (1971), Cairns et al⁵⁰ (1989), Stromquist⁵¹ (1989), Ilon and Moock⁵² (1991), Fuller et al⁵³ (1995), Colclough, Rose and Tembon⁵⁴ (2000), Higgins et al⁵⁵ (2007), Mike et al⁵⁶ (2008). All these studies have framed various determinants (both proximate and distant) at their convenience and explained their studies in respect of enrolment, retention and dropout of children. But according to the present author, there has remained a less-explored area of a determinant of school dropout of children, and that is the purpose of this paper. According to various data obtained, it has been found by the present author that Incarceration of Parents can well be accepted as a proximate determinant for school dropout of children. But this study is limited to West Bengal only. For the sake of reference, we have relied upon various Government reports and statistics as primary data and used them at our convenience.

⁴⁹Levy, M. B. (1971, Feb.). *Determinants of Primary School Dropouts in Developing Countries*. COMPARATIVE EDUCATION REVIEW, VOL. 15 (No. 1), pp. 44-58.

⁵⁰Cairns, R. B., Cairns, B. D., & Neckerman, H. J. (1989). *Early School Dropout: Configurations and Determinants*. CHILD DEVELOPMENT, VOL. 60 (No. 6), pp. 1437-1452.

⁵¹Stromquist, N. P. (1989). *Determinants of Educational Participation and Achievement of Women in the Third World: A Review of the Evidence and a Theoretical Critique*. REVIEW OF EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH, VOL. 59 (No. 2), PP. 143-183.

⁵²Ilon, L., & Moock, P. (1991). *School Attributes, Household Characteristics, and Demand for Schooling: A Case Study of Rural Peru*. INTERNATIONAL REVIEW OF EDUCATION, VOL.37 (No. 4), pp. 429-451.

⁵³Fuller, B., Singer, J. D., & Keiley, M. (1995). *Why do Daughters Leave School in Southern Africa? Family Economy and Mothers*. SOCIAL FORCES, VOL. 74 (No. 2), pp. 657-681.

⁵⁴Colclough, C., Rose, P., & Tembon, M. (2000). *Gender inequalities in primary schooling: The roles of poverty and adverse cultural practice*. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT, VOL. 20 (No. 1), pp. 5-27.

⁵⁵O’Higgins, N., D’Amato, M., Caroleo, F. E., & Barone, A. (2007). *Gone for Good? Determinants of School Dropout in Southern Italy*. GIORNALE DEGLI ECONOMISTI E ANNALI DI ECONOMIA, VOL. 66 (No. 2), pp. 207-246.

⁵⁶Mike, I. O., Nakajjo, A., & Isoke, D. (2008). *Socioeconomic Determinants of Primary School Dropout: The Logistic Model Analysis*. ECONOMIC POLICY RESEARCH CENTRE.

3.2 Interpretation of Data for West Bengal

Although there is no direct correlation between the criminality of the children of those whose parents are incarcerated, we can extrapolate our interpretation of the prison data and infer that those children whose parents are incarcerated, and live outside the prison, are shunned away by our society and treated as *potential criminals*, and eventually end up leaving school. Some can even lead themselves to get behind the bars as a consequence of their poor social acceptance, and subsequently becoming criminals.

3.2.1 West Bengal Prison Statistics Data

Educational qualification-wise data of prison population: Let us consider the following tables first, depicting prison demographics over the years in connection to the **educational qualification** of the prison population:

Educational Qualification	Convicts (male+female)	Under-trials (male+female)	Total
Illiterate	3493	9730	13223
Below Class X	1845	4724	6569
Class X & above	908	2123	3031
Graduate	139	448	22
Post-Graduate	23	54	587
Technical Degree/ Diploma	13	3	16

Table 3: Demographic particulars of West Bengal prison inmates (31st December, 2018)

Educational Qualification	Convicts (male+female)	Under-trials (male+female)	Total
Illiterate	4255	10674	14929
Below Class X	1963	5962	7925
Class X & above	339	2260	2599
Graduate	108	5	113
Post-Graduate	21	1	22
Technical Degree/ Diploma	9	5	16

Table 4: Demographic particulars of West Bengal prison inmates (31st December, 2019)

Educational Qualification	Convicts (male+female)	Under-trials (male+female)	Total
Illiterate	1982	8735	10717
Below Class X	2170	7033	9203
Class X & above	983	3536	4519
Graduate	193	674	867
Post-Graduate	29	110	139
Technical Degree/ Diploma	10	56	66

Table 5: Demographic particulars of West Bengal prison inmates (31st December, 2020)

Educational Qualification	Convicts (male+female)	Under-trials (male+female)	Total
Illiterate	860	9091	9951
Below Class X	1275	7946	9221
Class X & above	615	4492	5107
Graduate	114	872	986
Post-Graduate	18	129	147
Technical Degree/ Diploma	72	47	119

Table 6: Demographic particulars of West Bengal prison inmates (31st December, 2021)

Educational Qualification	Convicts (male+female)	Under-trials (male+female)	Total
Illiterate	1577	9971	11548
Below Class X	1990	8427	10417
Class X & above	849	4101	4950
Graduate	173	944	1117
Post-Graduate	32	204	236
Technical Degree/ Diploma	61	59	120

Table 7: Demographic particulars of West Bengal prison inmates (31st December, 2022)

Age-group wise data of prison population: Now let us consider the data of West Bengal Prison Statistics from a point of view of **age-group** of the prison population. All this data has been selectively taken for the purpose of this paper.

Type	16 & above but below 18 years	18 & above but below 30 years	30 & above but below 50 years
Convicts (Male+Female)	1	1066	2521
Under-trials (Male+Female)	50	6727	6925

Table 8: Age-specific particulars of West Bengal prison inmates (31st December, 2018)

Type	16 & above but below 18 years	18 & above but below 30 years	30 & above but below 50 years
Convicts (Male+Female)	0	1271	2740
Under-trials (Male+Female)	42	7688	7499

Table 9: Age-specific particulars of West Bengal prison inmates (31st December, 2019)

Type	16 & above but below 18 years	18 & above but below 30 years	30 & above but below 50 years
Convicts (Male+Female)	0	700	2675
Under-trials (Male+Female)	0	8179	8757

Table 10: Age-specific particulars of West Bengal prison inmates (31st December, 2020)

Type	16 & above but below 18 years	18 & above but below 30 years	30 & above but below 50 years
Convicts (Male+Female)	0	460	1543
Under-trials (Male+Female)	0	9948	9221

Table 11: Age-specific particulars of West Bengal prison inmates (31st December, 2021)

Type	16 & above but below 18 years	18 & above but below 30 years	30 & above but below 50 years
Convicts (Male+Female)	0	576	2334
Under-trials (Male+Female)	0	10469	9767

Table 12: Age-specific particulars of West Bengal prison inmates (31st December, 2022)

From the above tables we can extrapolate a hypothesis as to the connection between the school drop-out and the parents who are being incarcerated in prisons and jails in the state of West Bengal. It is seen from Table Nos 3-6 that the educational qualifications of the convicts as well as the under-trials can be taken as an indicator for the commission of

crimes by the persons — more populated the cells, lower the educational qualification. It has a direct connection between school drop-out of the perpetrators, but not so direct with their incarcerated parents. For this let us focus on the Table Nos 8-12, where we can find the age-wise data of prison population, which show us that the most populated are the age brackets 18-29 and 30-49, both as convicts as well as under-trials. It can be easily inferred from this that the children population of these age-bracket are not treated by the society very well and their school attendance is poor. In an article⁵⁷ it was commented that more than 1800 children of the age bracket 1 month to 6 years languish mercilessly in Indian prisons and are growing up in the most horrific circumstances with their imprisoned mothers⁵⁸. This simple commentary can be seen as a large loophole in our criminal justice system, as well as our legal system since the RTE Act imposes obligation on the State agencies for implementation of Article 21A of our Constitution targeting the age-bracket 6-14 years.

The Tables 3-12 depict a picture, where the effects of incarceration is found indirectly, that is to say, those who are within the age-group of persons going to schools, and those who are in the age group of persons who are potential parents. The educational profiles of the prison inmates speak for the fact that those who drop out at the earliest level, are prone to commit crimes more.

Women with children in West Bengal prisons: Now let us see the present state of affairs inside the West Bengal prisons by finding out the picture of women prison-inmates with children in the following table. It is to be noted that while preparing the report for the years 2018 and 2019, NCRB reported that no report of these years had been found for West Bengal, and hence for the purpose of reference, the year 2017 was taken.

⁵⁷Rajesh Trichur Venkiteswaran, *India: Guiltless Children in Prison* (2018), <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/the-interpreter/india-guiltless-children-in-prison>; accessed on 8th February, 2025

⁵⁸Shreya Mahajan, *Governance 'Without' and 'Beyond' the State Law: A Classic Illustration of Structural Violence*, ILI LAW REVIEW-2023 (Summer, e-ISSN-0976-1489) (2018), http://www.ili.ac.in/pdf/16..Shreya_Mahajan_F

Year	No. of convict women prisoners with children	No. of children of convict women prisoners	No. of undertrial women prisoners with children	No. of children of undertrial women prisoners	Total no. of children inside prison
2017	64	72	83	120	192
2020	19	22	119	137	159
2021	17	28	132	151	179
2022	24	34	123	151	185

Table 13: Number of women prisoners with children in prisons of West Bengal

It can be seen from Table 13 that a total of 715 children were documented to be within the prison environment in West Bengal with their mothers. These children are within the age-group 0-6 years, as the law requires a children below 6 years of age should be with his/her mother in prison. As per NCRB Prison Statistics data from 2018-2022, accessed on-line by the present author, no Borstal School was found for the state of West Bengal, instead, there are number of Juvenile Justice Homes.⁵⁹ But these Borstal Schools or juvenile justice homes are meant for the juvenile delinquents only. Then what about those children who are over 6 years of age and so, not residing within the prison with their incarcerated mothers? These are under the purview of RTE Act 2009, and the State agency has an obligation towards their compulsory schooling until they attain 14 years of age. But due to social stigma, and/ or lack societal acceptance, they tend to absent frequently from classes resulting in poor academic performance. But this has not been considered to be used as an indicator by any Government agency collecting and sampling raw data regarding school drop-out patterns. There is definitely a direct relationship between parents' incarceration and school drop-out by their children, no matter the children stay with them inside the jails and then come out after 6 years of age, or they are already above 6 years of age when their parents go to jail. There are ample provisions in law⁶⁰ for minor and juvenile delinquents and observing their psycho-social development and re-integrating them within the societal set-up through various Government as well as non-Governmental agencies, but those of incarcerated parents (whether one or both) do not constitute such a class to be observed

⁵⁹The detailed list of West Bengal Juvenile Justice Homes can found here— https://wbscps.in/User/juvenile_justice_homes accessed on 9th February, 2025

⁶⁰Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015

separately within the framework of any codified legal structure.

According to a recent report,⁶¹ between the time period 2020-2024, sixty two babies were born inside West Bengal jails. Most of the women who were brought to the jails were pregnant at that time. This was in connection to the matter titled *Inhuman conditions in 1,382 prisons* in the Apex Court, where this report was submitted by the ADG&IG, Correctional Services, West Bengal. We can foresee the grim future of these children from this small information.

3.2.2 Interpretation of National Sample Survey Report

In this study, the National Sample Survey 75th Round Report⁶² titled *Household Social Consumption on Education in India* has been considered. Let us first look at the following table, extracted for West Bengal data in comparison with the all-India data:

Reference	Rural Male	Rural Female	Urban Male	Urban Female
West Bengal	24.9	24.7	19.9	20.4
all-India	13.2	14.7	9.5	9.7

Table 14: Percentage of persons dropped out among ever enrolled persons of age 3 to 35 years for West Bengal (*male includes transgender*)

Drop-out from school means those children who ever enrolled for education but who are not currently attending school. NSS has listed major indicators for this, such as

1. not interested in education
2. financial constraints
3. engaged in domestic activities
4. engaged in economic activities
5. unable to cope up with studies/ failure in studies
6. completed desired level/ class
7. preparation for competitive examination and

⁶¹<https://www.deccanherald.com/india/west-bengal/62-babies-born-in-four-years-in-west-bengal-most-women-prisoners-were-already-expecting-sc-told-2894164>

⁶²NSS Report No. 585(75/25.2/1), July 2017 - June 2018

8. other; (*'other' includes: timings of educational institution not suitable, language/medium of instruction used unfamiliar, inadequate number of teachers, quality of teachers not satisfactory, route to educational institution not safe, unfriendly atmosphere at school and residual 'other' reasons.*)

Thus the extensive NSS data is silent about incarcerated parents as a possible direct indicator for school drop-out of children. This is the reason why this study is crucial and, at the same time, cumbersome, too.

3.3 Other Relevant Studies Regarding Parental Incarceration and School Drop-out

It is shown that (Shlafer, Reedy & Davis, 2017⁶³) parents' incarceration is a risk factor for children's academic and school-based outcomes. The problems of these children (who do not live with their parents inside the prison) have been identified as grade retention (Turney & Haskins, 2014⁶⁴), behavioural problems (Hanlon *et al*, 2005⁶⁵), chronic stress (Murray, Farrington & Sekol, 2012⁶⁶). It is also seen that students with currently incarcerated mothers are more likely to be suspended, fail classes, drop out of school, and have extended absences from school⁶⁷.

⁶³Shlafer, R. J., Reedy, T., & Davis, L. (2017). *School-based outcomes among youth with incarcerated parents: Differences by school setting*. JOURNAL OF SCHOOL HEALTH, 87(9), 687-695.

⁶⁴Turney, K., & Haskins, A. R. (2014). *Falling behind? Children's early grade retention after paternal incarceration*. SOCIOLOGY OF EDUCATION, 87(4), 241-258.

⁶⁵Hanlon, T. E., Blatchley, R. J., Bennett-Sears, T., O'Grady, K. E., Rose, M., & Callaman, J. M. (2005). *Vulnerability of children of incarcerated addict mothers: Implications for preventive intervention*. CHILDREN AND YOUTH SERVICES REVIEW, 27(1), 67-84.

⁶⁶Murray, J., Farrington, D. P., & Sekol, I. (2012). *Children's antisocial behavior, mental health, drug use, and educational performance after parental incarceration: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. PSYCHOLOGICAL BULLETIN, 138(2), 175.

⁶⁷Trice, A. D., & Brewster, J. (2004). *The effects of maternal incarceration on adolescent children*. JOURNAL OF POLICE AND CRIMINAL PSYCHOLOGY, 19(1), 27-35.

4 Conclusion or Way Forward?

Why are we pressing so hard? I mean to say, why are we trying to find a way, an indicator, so badly, which we can correlate with school drop-out of children of incarcerated parents? The phenomenon of school drop-out in West Bengal, and all-over India has been studied so extensively and almost exhaustively that it seems that no more indicator is left behind to examine. Yet, we are concerned here with another specific indicator. Why? Because Judge Jerome Frank once said: *In a democracy, court belongs not to the lawyers and judges but to the citizen.* The Indian courts, with its heavy burden of cases, with a piecemeal of persons acting as Hon'ble Judges and Magistrates, suffers with a cyclic syndrome of delay, arrears and pendency (Ghosh, 2018⁶⁸). If we see the number of under-trials in the tables taken as a reference in this paper, we can understand that the Indian courts, in their harsh reality, are not acting for the people of this country. The rate of conviction in IPC (now BNS) crimes is so low, and delivery of justice in the lower courts is so slow, that the incarceration period of persons inside jails sometimes becomes more than the sentence period. Hence, the connection between parental incarceration and children's school drop-out is not a dichotomous problem, but a multitudinous one. The lengthy incarceration period of under-trial prisoners affects adversely the school-going sons and daughters of the accused and this initiates a chain reaction of generational incarceration. We are not here to speak for incarcerated parents, but for the speedy delivery of justice. The wheel of criminal justice system, if remains retarded even after almost eighty years of independence, and in effect, begets children of injustice who do not have access to proper education and psycho-social development solely due to their parents' unjustified incarceration, then our Constitutional morality is vitiated.

Hence, if we are serious and sincere enough for our future generation, we have to include in our Governmental statistical framework an indicator which will show the inter-relation between the parental incarceration and their children's school drop-out patterns, and then only true economic, political and social justice will be delivered.

⁶⁸Ghosh, Y. (2018). *Indian judiciary: an analysis of the cyclic syndrome of delay, arrears and pendency.* ASIAN JOURNAL OF LEGAL EDUCATION, 5(1), 21-39.